

2020 Report. Cheers to the great MetaDocencia community!

2020 is over, a year of many challenges, uncertainties and changes. MetaDocencia was born in this context as a response to the need and urgency imposed by the pandemic, to offers tools for making a quick and effective switch to online classes. The proposal was embraced and amplified from its very beginnings by many educators in Argentina and abroad. MetaDocencia has established itself as a collaborative and inclusive community to support Spanish-speaking teachers, that shares evidence-based educational methods and provides open resources to foster effective teaching practices.

Those of us who make MetaDocencia are happy and thankful for the time shared during this difficult time. We renew our commitment on 2021, a year that welcomes us to more and better offers to learn and teach in community.

While we work on what's next, we invite you to review all the good things that brought 2020 in MetaDocencia.

[Summary of the 2020 Report as slides](#)

A lot has happened

MetaDocencia was born on March 16th 2020 as an initiative of four people, early joined by another one to constitute the current **Core Team**. More volunteers joined late and we now have 10 Contributors and 5 Advisory Team members. Their participation in daily activities and monthly meetings is essential to sustain the activities of MetaDocencia.

More than 1200 teachers from 20 countries showed interest in our courses. Most came from the city of Buenos Aires and its surroundings, but we have shared the classroom with teachers from all provinces in Argentina. As we deal with content in Spanish, and thanks to the presence of Spanish-speaking

individuals throughout the world, our reach exceeds Latin America. Our courses have been taken by more than 700 educators from Argentina, Uruguay, Bolivia, Chile, Peru, Costa Rica, Mexico, Spain, and also in the United States of America, France, Canada and the United Kingdom.

Those teachers who took part in MetaDocencia deliver courses for all educational levels in different disciplines. From the classic subjects of Biology, Literature and Maths, to Robotics, Traumatology, Marketing and Architecture. Most of the participants teach STEM disciplines, followed by teachers in Social Sciences. Considering the size of their classes, MetaDocencia could be reaching more than 19,000 students!.

We met at many courses

Already present in the [web](#), on [Twitter](#) and with an active [pre-registration form](#), on March 27th 2020 we delivered the first edition of our flagship course [Introduction to online teaching essentials](#). We had 41 editions of this course up to October 26th, 34 of those as the standard workshop (with 494 participants) and 7 adapted 'à la carte' (137 participants).

Moreover, we gave 8 brief courses How to teach (and do other stuff) on-line for 88 participants from the [National Agricultural Technology Institute \(INTA\)](#). We also piloted two new courses, the [Zoom Workshop](#) and [Generating interactive tutorials with the {learnr} package](#), the latter delivered as part of the *LatinR* conference.

Over four days in August 2020, three Core Team members delivered the first The Carpentries Instructor Training course by MetaDocencia to 'train the trainers'. As a result, 19 participants were certified as Instructors in the international project [The Carpentries](#) that aims to teach computational and data science skills to researchers.

We had an online presence

Our website hosts [25 original articles](#) (5 of those [in English](#)) written during 2020 by the MetaDocencia community. The first post was published along

with the beginning of our workshops in March 2020 to present the [Learner profiles for our Introductory courses](#) (*in Spanish*).

These articles gather advices, tutorials, experiences and opinions. Some are cross-published in other websites; for example, [this article on our website](#) is the Spanish version of our post [Building capacities to teach data science in Latin America](#) for the RStudio Education blog.

Social networks were essential to amplify our initiative. In November 2020 we reached 1000 followers on [Twitter](#). We ended 2020 with 1100 followers and over 500 tweets. 71 people are subscribed to our [YouTube channel](#) where we published 6 videos that got 1032 views. With 593 views, our most popular video is [Introduction to online teaching essentials](#) (*in Spanish*).

Our [Slack workspace](#) is the virtual and open meeting room for 376 participants in MetaDocencia. It is the place to share resources, experiences, support and questions, built by the communitary effort through 18295 messages sent in 2020. The channel is kept active from the beginnings of MetaDocencia, peaking at 78 active members on the week of April 27th 2020 and 40 active members on a day in July 21st, with almost 1000 messages sent in December. The workspace is open to anyone wishing to take part (37% of the messages were seen on open channels) but also allows the organization of community activities in closed channels (40% of the messages sent on those and 17% as direct messages between individuals.)

The internal or public resources of MetaDocencia are shared through our [Github repositories](#). We actively promote the use of [Creative Commons licenses](#) and we have written a blogpost on how to [share educational material and maintain authorship](#).

We participated in many events

Following is the timeline of the many and diverse events in which MetaDocencia was present during 2020.

- 06/21/2020 - **Meetup R-Ladies Buenos Aires**
In the 5th Meetup of R-Ladies Buenos Aires, **María Nantón** recommends MetaDocencia in her talk Visualizando Datos: Especial “#30DíasDeGráficos” (*Visualizing Data: ‘#30DaysOfGraphics’ Special*).
- 07/01/2020 - **MetaMeetup R-Ladies**
In the R-Ladies MetaMeetup, the talk Cómo hacer una reunión virtual inolvidable (sin morir en el intento) (*How to make an unforgettable online meeting (and don’t die trying)*) was given by **Paola Corrales** and **Yanina Bellini Saibene** with the help of **Laura Acion**, **Patricia Loto** and **Paloma Rojas-Saunero**. 19 R-Ladies chapters from 8 countries took part, with more than 100 participants.
- 07/07/2020 - **useR!2020**
Several of our members took part in the online panel Comunidades de práctica en Latinoamérica (*Communities of practice in Latin America*) in which **Yanina Bellini Saibene** mentioned MetaDocencia.
- 07/17/2020 - **useR!2020**
Yanina Bellini Saibene and **Greg Wilson** mentioned MetaDocencia in the panel Supporting diversity in the R community at useR!2020.
- 07/23/2020 - **CarpentryCon**
Laura Acion presented MetaDocencia while attending the panel Carpentries Instructors’ Experiences from Teaching Online.
- 07/29/2020 - **PEARC20 (Practice & Experience in Advanced Research Computing)**
Kate Hertweck mentioned MetaDocencia in her talk From Novice to Expert: Supporting All Levels of Computational Expertise in Reproducible Research Methods, also published as an **article**.
- 09/14/2020 - **Seminarios sobre Matemática Aplicada FAMAF**
Yanina Bellini Saibene presented MetaDocencia in her talk Ciencias de Datos en el sector agropecuario (*Data Science in the agricultural sector*).
- 09/29/2020 - **Open-source Community Call**
Laura Acion presented MetaDocencia. MetaTeaching: Teaching to Teach in Spanish in the Open-source Community Call co-organized by **Dryad**, **FORCE11** and **eLife**.

- 10/02/2020 - **LatinR**
The Workshop Introducción al ABC para enseñar online (*Introduction to online teaching essentials*) was delivered by **Mariela Rajngewerc** and **Yanina Bellini Saibene**.
- 10/03/2020 - **LatinR**
The Workshop Generando tutoriales interactivos con el paquete {learnr} (*Generating interactive tutorials with the {learnr} package*) was delivered by **Yanina Bellini Saibene** and **Paola Corrales**.
- 10/22/2020 - **Open Life Science**
Internal presentation for the second cohort of Open Life Science by **Laura Acion**.
- 10/23/2020 - **Plataforma de Asistencia Estadística INTA**
Yanina Bellini Saibene presents MetaDocencia in her talk Comunidades de práctica para I+D y T+E: R y colegas (*Communities of practice for R+D and T+E: R and colleagues*) for the Statistical Assistance Platform of **INTA** and the **Red INTAJoven**.
- 10/27/2020 - **IEEE International Conference on Image Processing**
Laura Acion presented MetaDocencia in her talk Educational Communities of Practice for an Inclusive Artificial Intelligence.
- 11/02/2020 - **XV Jornadas de Informática en Salud**
Paloma Rojas-Saunero presented Metadocencia in her talk Comunidades internacionales para el avance de la ciencia de datos de salud en América Latina (*International communities to advance data science in health in Latin America*) shared with **Jesica Formoso** and assisted by **Laura Acion**.
- 11/12/2020 - **NoviembreHD**
The talk Una experiencia en comunidades de práctica de Software, Ciencia y Datos (*An experience in communities of practice in Software, Science and Data*) was given by **Yanina Bellini Saibene**, who mentioned her experience in creating a new community like MetaDocencia.
- 11/12/2020 - **OpenEducationConference**
The talk MetaDocencia. Volunteer Community Building for Teaching in Spanish, Online, and on Short Notice was presented by **Paola Corrales**, assisted by **Laura Acion** and **Nicolás Palopoli**.

- 11/17/2020 - **PyConAR**
Mariela Rajngewerc and **Patricia Loto**, assisted by **Nicolás Palopoli**, presented the talk Buenas prácticas para enseñar programación online (*Good practices for teaching programming online*).

We received very positive feedback

Through post-course surveys, by email or on Twitter, we received many messages of appreciation and gratitude, which helped us a lot to value and sustain the effort we put into MetaDocencia. Thanks for all the love!

"The course was excellent. You gave me back the will to teach. I hated everything about having to teach online, but you showed me that you can do something nice. I couldn't even imagine the possibility of this being feasible. Teaching online can be much more humane than I could have ever imagined." – translation of a message in Spanish by Emmanuel Iarussi, participant of our course **Introduction to online teaching essentials**

We share below some tweets that filled us with joy.

Tweet translation: Personally I recommend the courses by @metadocencia for this and for modern, evidence-based pedagogy. Mind blowing!

Romi
@romi_nahir · [Seguir](#)

En respuesta a @romi_nahir

Mi primer cuatri fue desorganizado y muy difícil de encargar, gracias a la ayuda de [@metadocencia](#) y la certificación docente de [@thecarpentries](#) aprendí un montón de metodologías nuevas y de formas de acercarme a los alumnos detrás de la pantalla...

12:57 p. m. · 21 dic. 2020

Tweet translation: My first term was disorganized and very hard to face, thanks to the help of [@metadocencia](#) and the instructor certification of [@thecarpentries](#) I learnt a lot of new methodologies and ways of getting closer to students behind the screen...

Martin Ezequiel Farina
@HallucigeniaOK · [Seguir](#)

Respondiendo a @_luciarp_ @Exactas_UBA y 3 más

Me cuelo para decir que [@metadocencia](#) fue alta herramienta y que de todas las materias virtuales en la que estuve como docente, la que mejor salió, fue en la que les tres docentes hicimos el Taller. No lo decimos nosotros. Miren las encuestas :)

11:57 p. m. · 12 dic. 2020

Tweet translation: I jump in to say that [@metadocencia](#) was a top tool and of all the virtual subjects I took part as teacher, the best one happened when the three teachers had taken the Workshop. It's not our words. Look at the feedback :).

Enzo Ferrante
@enzoferrante · [Seguir](#)

Impecable el curso de 3hs de MetaDocencia que nos dieron hoy @_lacion_ y @ni_airo , ordenando conceptos sobre cómo encarar la enseñanza online! 🙌🙌

Fundamental para quienes hicimos/hacemos/haremos docencia online en pandemia

Más info -> metadocencia.netlify.app

12:11 p. m. · 24 oct. 2020

Tweet translation: Flawless 3-hour MetaDocencia workshop today by @_lacion_ and @ni_airo, putting in order concepts about how to deal with online teaching! Essential for those who did/do/will teach online in pandemic.

Walter Sosa Escudero
@wsosaescudero · [Seguir](#)

La gente de @metadocencia junto a @_lacion_ hace un espectacular laburo "siglo XXI" en la enseñanza de cosas de datos

8:42 p. m. · 20 oct. 2020

Tweet translation: The people at @metadocencia together with @_lacion_ make a spectacular XXI Century job in teaching data stuff.
[@metadocencia](#) [@mariela_rajng](#) [@yabellini](#) En relación a "Intro al ABC para enseñar on-line"

Les quiero felicitar, una maravilla tode, excelente lo q hacen x todes

En estos momentos de crisis, su ayuda es el camino para salir adelante

No bajen los brazos. Este mundo necesita d uds!

– Cristian Rodriguez (@Cristia42038941) **October 2, 2020**

Tweet translation: Regarding “Introduction to online teaching essentials” I want to congratulate you, everything wonderful, excellent what you do for everyone. In this moments of crysis, your help is the way to move forward. Don’t give up. This world needs you!

Sergio Garcia Mora
@sergiogarciamor · [Seguir](#)

Ayer terminé la primera edición de mí curso de Introducción a R para RRHH.
Que bueno que hice el curso de [@metadocencia](#) porque estoy muy feliz por cómo salió.

Data4HR @data4hr

Ayer finalizó la primera edición del curso "Introducción a R para RRHH" 🎉 y estos son los primeros prints de pantalla del trabajo que hicieron los participantes. 🙌

Gracias a todos los que se sumaron!!! #BetterWithData #R4HR #RStats_ES #PeopleAnalytics #RRHH

2:40 p. m. · 31 jul. 2020

Tweet translation: Yesterday I finished the first edition of my course Introduction to R for HR. So glad I took the course by [@metadocencia](#) because I am very happy with the way it went.

REDBIO Argentina
@REDBIOArgentina · [Seguir](#)

Esta mañana hice el curso de [@metadocencia](#). Sinceramente una de las mejores cosas que he hecho en esta cuarentena. Si necesitan dar clases/reuniones/talleres mediante plataformas virtuales sigan esta cuenta. 🙌🙌🙌

12:22 p. m. · 18 jul. 2020

Tweet translation: This morning I did the course by [@metadocencia](#). Honestly one of the best things I did on this quarantine. If you need to give classes/meetings/workshops on virtual platforms follow this account.

Pau ❤️
@PauBaires_ · [Seguir](#)

Acabo de terminar el curso de Introducción a la enseñanza online de [@metadocencia](#) y no puedo estar más contenta. Gratuito, súper interesante y útil, una excelente herramienta para empezar a mejorar y configurar nuestras prácticas docentes en este nuevo contexto. Inscripción:

MetaDocencia @metadocencia
¿Estás dando clases online pero sentís que no llegas a tus alumnos? No te pierdas nuestro curso online para mejorar tus clases. Anotate
👉 bit.ly/metadoc-form y sumate a nuestra comunidad
join.slack.com/t/metadocencia...

12:07 p. m. · 15 may. 2020

Tweet translation: I just finished the course Introduction to online teaching essentials by [@metadocencia](#) and I couldn't be happier. Free, super interesting and useful, an excellent tool to start to improve and setup our teaching practices in this new context.

Mariana Fernandez ❤️
@mafebahia · [Seguir](#)

Para docentes q estén lidiando con la virtualidad d cuarentena, les recomiendo mucho el curso gratuito de [@metadocencia](#)
Son 3 hrs d muy buenos tips y consejos para mejorar esta migración del aula a la pantalla q estamos haciendo.

12:52 p. m. · 9 may. 2020

Tweet translation: For teachers dealing with virtuality in quarantine, I highly recommend the free course by [@metadocencia](#). It's 3 hours of very good tips and advice for improving the swith from the classroom to the screen that we are doing.

Valentín Alvarez
@valvarezmr · [Seguir](#)

A les docentes en la sala, aprovechen los recursos de metadocencia. Es de esas cosas que necesitabas y no lo sabías.

MetaDocencia @metadocencia

📌 ¿Necesitas virtualizar 🧑‍🏫 tus clases y no sabes por donde empezar? Toma nuestro 📄 curso introductorio gratuito 👉 bit.ly/metadoc-form y sumate a nuestra comunidad 🗣️ en #slack join.slack.com/t/metadocencia...

9:45 p. m. · 14 abr. 2020

Tweet translation: To the teachers in the room, take advantage of the resources of metadocencia. It's one of those things you didn't know you needed.

Greg Wilson @gvwilson@mastodon.social
@gvwilson · [Seguir](#)

"Building capacities to teach data science in Latin America" a wonderful initiative that is making a real difference

education.rstudio.com

Building capacities to teach data science in Latin America - RStudio...

The birth and growth of MetaDocencia in Latin America to nurture a community of Spanish-speaking educators in 2020 and beyond.

4:10 p. m. · 18 dic. 2020

Dr. Kari L. Jordan
@DrKariLJordan · [Seguir](#)

Attending the Open Source Community call I learned about [@metadocencia](#) and I cannot be more excited about this project!

12:27 p. m. · 29 sept. 2020

Dr. Sara El-Gebali 🇺🇸 [yalahowy@fairpoints.social](#)
@yalahowy · [Seguir](#)

Looking forward to learning more about [@metadocencia](#), this is exactly the type of work we should be supporting and hearing more about ❤️ truly amazing! ❤️

Laura Ación, on Mastodon @lacion@scicomm.xyz @_lacion_

Hoy conocí OpenCIDER de la mano de @yalahowy. Es una plataforma que se ocupa poner en el foco en las necesidades de lugares con bajos recursos para hacer ciencia abierta, equitativa e inclusiva.

Tienen una web y un Slack para seguir de cerca 🙌👩👨👧👦

5:13 p. m. · 29 sept. 2020

We were supported from the start

To start out MetaDocencia it was essential to have the support of [R-Ladies Buenos Aires](#) and [Estación Experimental Agropecuaria Anguil](#) from INTA. We were able to benefit from funding from the [Open Bioinformatics Foundation](#) to cover communication and planning costs. Besides, it was crucial to have access to the open teaching material shared by [Greg Wilson](#), [R-Studio Education](#) and [The Carpentries](#). To all these people and organizations, thank you very much!

We have big plans!

Our plans for 2021 are exciting. Our guiding light will be to take care of the community that trusts in MetaDocencia, ensuring our continuity, giving more and better resources and implementing the means to bring the community to those in need of it. Apart from the well-known ones, very soon we'll be offering new courses that are already in advanced stages of development. We'll scale our registration process to facilitate the process of designing how and what to learn. Moreover, we'll implement ways to measure our impact effectively and thus help spread and replicate our experience.

Shared joy is doubled; shared pain is halved

Thank you for joining us in 2020. We look forward to seeing you in 2021 too!